

Utilization of Quizizz as a Formative Assessment Media in the Interspace Interaction Material

Ilah Armilah

Lampung University

Corresponding Author: Ilah Armilah 2223031003@students.unila.ac.id

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Quizizz, Formative Assessment Media, Interspace Interactions

Received : 22, October

Revised : 21, November

Accepted: 30, December

©2023 Armilah: This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

ABSTRACT

Formative assessment using the Quizizz application can be a formative assessment medium for Interspatial Interaction material in the 7th grade social studies subject. This research took 28 class VII B students at SMP Negeri 4 Bukit Kemuning as research subjects. This research method uses a combination research method (Mixed Methods). The research results showed that digital-based formative assessment, in this case using the Quizizz application, can foster interest and motivation to learn in class VII students at SMP Negeri 4 Bukit Kemuning so that they aspire to get better results in the next assessment. And based on observations during the assessment, students looked enthusiastic.

INTRODUCTION

In a learning process, evaluation or assessment is something that must be done to measure students' success in a teaching material (Idrus, 2019; Rohim, 2021). The final aim of the evaluation carried out is to measure whether students understand the material, or are even able to apply the knowledge they have acquired in real life (Addiin, 2014; Aulia, et al., 2020). One way to find out the extent of students' understanding of a teaching material is through learning evaluation. When the learning process is seen as a process of changing student behavior, the role of evaluation and assessment in the learning process becomes very important. Assessment in the learning process is a process for collecting, analyzing and interpreting information to determine the level of achievement of learning objectives (Magdalena, et al., 2020). So, learning evaluation is the process of collecting, analyzing and interpreting information systematically to determine the achievement of learning objectives (Muhammad, et al., 2021). The aim is to collect information that can be used as a basis for determining the level of progress, development and achievement of student learning, as well as the effectiveness of teacher teaching.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The learning process is an intentional (Conscious) activity by students with direction, guidance or assistance from the teacher to achieve a change. The expected changes include cognitive (Knowledge), affective (Attitudes and Behavior) and psychomotor (Skills) aspects (El Fiah and Purbaya, 2016; Suardi, 2018). Learning evaluation includes three aspects, these three aspects are:

1. The cognitive domain contains behaviors that emphasize intellectual aspects such as knowledge, understanding and thinking skills.
2. The affective domain contains behaviors that emphasize aspects of feelings and emotions such as interests, attitudes, appreciation and ways of adapting.
3. The psychomotor domain contains behaviors that emphasize aspects of motor skills such as handwriting, typing, swimming and operating machines.

Learning evaluation consists of measurement and assessment activities, where the process goes through three stages, namely the planning stage, implementation stage, and results processing and reporting stage (Widiana, 2016; Amri & Tharikh, 2018).

Student assessment activities are an important component in teaching and learning activities in schools (Mustika, et al. 2021). To obtain information about the achievement of the results of the student's learning process in accordance with the objectives that have been set, an assessment of learning outcomes is needed (Mustopa, et al., 2021).

Keeping up with the times and the needs of students' abilities in utilizing information and communication technology, in this case formative assessment using digital media, Quizizz. It is hoped that the use of Quizizz can become a platform that can attract interest and increase students' learning motivation.

Formative assessments are generally carried out during the learning process of a unit/chapter/competency. Can be done at the beginning or throughout the learning process (Kemdikbud & Abduh, 2019). The purpose of formative assessment is to determine the development of students' mastery of a unit/chapter/competency being studied (Adinda, 2021; Sumantri, et al., 2021). The final output of formative assessment is as a basis for improving the learning process of a unit/chapter/competency being studied so that students achieve optimal mastery (Adinda, 2021; Muslih, 2022). The results of the formative assessment are not used to determine report card grades for promotion, graduation or other important decisions (Sabariah, 2020).

METHODOLOGY

The method used in this research is a combined research method (Mixed Methods). Mixed methods research is a research approach that combines or associates qualitative and quantitative forms (Mulyanah & Andriani, 2021). Through a quantitative approach, researchers obtained information regarding the number of students who participated in the questionnaire and the number and percentage of their answers. And with a qualitative description approach, researchers can see the percentage change in interest and learning motivation of class VII students at SMP Negeri 4 Bukit Kemuning.

RESULTS AND DISSCUSION

There are three research stages, namely the pre-field stage, field work stage and data analysis stage (Moelong, 2017). The following is an explanation of each stage:

- 1. Pre-Field Stage:** At this stage the researcher determined the research subjects, namely students in class VII B of SMP Negeri 4 Bukit Kemuning, totaling 32 people but this would be reduced by the number of students who were not present during the formative assessment. Next, the researcher asked permission from the school principal. On the following day the researcher carried out pre-observations and also prepared instruments for research.
- 2. Field Work Stage:** At this stage, researchers began to observe behavior, faces and words uttered when students carried out formative assessment activities on Interspatial Interaction material using Quizizz. Researchers observed students' interest and learning motivation when using the Quizizz application. Researchers prepared instruments to obtain data in the form of student responses via Google Form. During the assessment process, researchers also took several photos for documentation.
- 3. Analysis Stage:** The data that has been obtained through observations and questionnaires will be analyzed according to the researcher's needs to complete the research.

In this study, researchers carried out disguised observations so that students did not realize that they were being observed by researchers. Because researchers want the results of these observations to be pure and not made up. Before conducting the research, the researcher made preliminary observations first to find out how students reacted, interested and motivated to learn when they were told that a paper-based formative assessment would be held.

The next instrument is the questionnaire guide. Questionnaires are used to see student perceptions, namely tools used by researchers to collect data in the form of a set of questions or written statements that must be answered by respondents (Sugiyono, 2016). The questionnaire consists of 10 statements and there are 3 specific questions related to quizzes, interests and learning motivation of students. To process the data obtained from the questionnaire it will be interpreted in the form of descriptions.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1. Utilization of the Quizizz Application:** The Quizizz application is online, which means it can be used easily if supported by an adequate internet network (Salsabila, 2020). The Quizizz application has advantages, including that it can be used easily and can be accessed anytime and anywhere, provided that a supporting internet network and quizzes are still available (Dayanti, et al., 2020). To use the Quizizz application on a smartphone, you can download the application via the Play Store or directly use the search engine. And those who use a computer can directly search for it in a search engine or go directly to the Quizizz.com.
- 2. Implementation of Social Studies Learning Assessment on Interspatial Interaction Material Through the Quizizz Application:** One week before carrying out the formative assessment, the researcher provided information about the time and assessment materials. Students are asked to bring smartphones and continue to follow the provisions that apply at school. Researchers collaborate with BK teachers in monitoring smartphone use. Students access the quiz link that has been shared in the WhatsApp Group or join the quiz with the quiz code. When all students have entered the quiz, the researcher clicks start. A total of 18 students or around 64.3% stated that the general appearance of Quizizz was very interesting, represented by a rating scale of 5. There was not a single student who thought that Quizizz was very uninteresting (scale 1). As many as 1 student or around 3.6% said it was not interesting (scale 2), as many as 10.7% of students said it was quite interesting (scale 3), and as many as 21.4% said it was interesting (scale 4). When asked which question was more interesting using paper-based assessments or using Quizizz, almost the majority of students stated that Quizizz was more interesting, namely 27 students or around 96.4%. In answering the question, does using Quizizz in formative assessment give you enthusiasm and motivation to learn better and be more enthusiastic? As

many as 89.3% or around 25 students answered yes, one student or around 3.8% answered no, and as many as 2 students or around 7.1% answered normal or no impact. The conclusion from the results of this research is that digital-based formative assessment, in this case using the Quizizz application, can foster interest and motivation to learn in class VII B students at SMP Negeri 4 Bukit Kemuning so that they aspire to get better results in the next assessment.

Figure 1. Results in the Next Assessment

The final result of implementing the formative assessment using Quizizz is that there is a champion card for the highest scorer, which increases the enthusiasm of the students and increases their determination so that in the next formative assessment their names can be recorded on the card.

FURTHER STUDY

1. There are various features available in the Quizizz application that can be utilized. So that future researchers can use the Quizizz application not only as an assessment medium but also as an interactive learning medium.
2. Because using Quizizz requires a stable internet network, the results of this research do not apply to schools or students who are in areas far from the reach of electricity and the internet.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author would like to thank those who have helped and supported so that this article can be completed.

REFERENCES

- Addiin, I. (2014). Implementation of the project-based learning (PjBL) learning model on the main material of acid and base solutions in class 11 IPA 1 of SMA Negeri 2 Karanganyar in the 2013/2014 academic year.
- Amri, A., & Tharihk, A. J. (2018). Development of project learning assessment tools on pollution and environmental damage. *DIDACTICS OF BIOLOGY: Journal of Biology Education Research*, 2(2), 103-112.
- Aswir At All. (2020). Kahoot and Quizizz-Based Digital Assessment Training for Elementary School Teachers Lab School FTP UMJ.
- Aulia, R. N., Rahmawati, R., & Permana, D. (2020). The important role of evaluating language learning in elementary schools. *BELAINDIKA Journal (Learning and Educational Innovation)*, 2(1), 1-9.
- Azzah Amany. (2020). Quizizz as a Media for Evaluation of Online Mathematics Lessons.
- Dayanti, R. N., Herlambang, A. D., & Wijoyo, S. H. (2020). The Influence of the Quality of Implementation of Powerpoint and Quizizz Assisted Lecture Learning Methods on Cognitive and Psychomotor Learning Outcomes in Printing Graphic Design Subjects at SMK Negeri 12 Malang. *Journal of Information Technology and Computer Science Development*, 4(4), 1189-1198.
- Destri Sambara Sitorus, Tri Nugroho Budi Santoso. (2022). Utilization of Quizizz as a Game-Based Learning Media During the Covid-19 Pandemic.
- Dhian Nuri Rahmawati, Ana Fitrotun Nisa, Dwi Astuti, Fajariyani, Sullyanti. (2022). Utilization of the Quizizz Application as a Media for Natural Science Learning Assessment.
- El Fiah, R., & Purbaya, A. P. (2016). Application of Tutoring in Improving Student Learning Outcomes at SMP Negeri 12 Bandar Lampung City in the 2015/2016 Academic Year. *Counseling: Journal of Guidance and Counseling (E-Journal)*, 3(2), 171-184.
- Ministry of Education and Culture, P. P. P., & Abduh, M. (2019). Formative assessment model in 21st century learning for elementary schools.
- Magdalena, I., Mulyani, F., Fitriyani, N., & Delvia, A. H. (2020). Basic Concepts of Elementary School Learning Evaluation at Bencongan 1 State Elementary School. *Pensa*, 2(1), 87-98.
- Maskar, S., Dewi, P. S., & Puspaningtyas, N. D. (2020). Online learning &

blended learning: comparison of learning outcomes from fully online and integrated methods. *Prisma*, 9(2), 154-166.

- Moleong, L. J. (2017). *Qualitative Research Methodology*. Bandung: PT Teen Rosdakarya.
- Muhammad, M., Widyaningrum, H. K., Al Masjid, A., Komariah, K., & Sumarwati, S. (2021). Implementation of Indonesian Language learning evaluation procedures at Pekanbaru Vocational School during the pandemic. *Stylistics: Journal of Language and Literature Education*, 14(2), 109-120.
- Mulyanah, N., & Andriani, A. (2021). Teacher Guidance and Training Strategy in Learning Using Google Applications in Online Learning to Increase Student Learning Effectiveness During the Covid-19 Pandemic. *Journal of Basic Education Research (JRPD)*, 2(1), 67.
- Muslih, M. (2022). Synergizing the Potential Power of Self, Peer and Teacher Assessment to Improve Student Learning Outcomes at School. *Humanist Education: Educational Assessment in Schools*, 1.
- Mustika, D., Ambiyar, A., & Aziz, I. (2021). The process of assessing learning outcomes for the 2013 curriculum in elementary schools. *Basicedu Journal*, 5(6), 6158-6167.
- Mustopa, A., Jasim, J., Basri, H., & Barlian, U. C. (2021). Analysis of Educational Assessment Standards. *Journal of Educational Management*, 9(1), 24-29.
- Pratama, N. D., Sari, Y. A., & Adikara, P. P. (2018). Sentiment Analysis of Consumer Reviews Using the Naive Bayes Method with Chi Square Feature Selection for Recommendations for Traditional Food Locations. *Journal of Information Technology and Computer Science Development*, 2(9), 2982-2988.
- Sabariah, S. (2020). Utilization of Evaluation Results and Reflection on Learning Evaluation Implementation. *Tazkiya: Journal of Islamic Education*, 9(2), 122-133.
- Salsabila, U. H., Habiba, I. S., Amanah, I. L., Istiqomah, N. A., & Difany, S. (2020). Utilization of the Quizzizz application as a learning medium in the midst of a pandemic for high school students. *Jambi University Applied Sciences Scientific Journal | JIITUJ |*, 4(2), 163-173.
- Sugian Noor. (2020). Use of Quizizz in Learning Assessment on Biology Scope Material to Improve Class X.6 Student Learning Outcomes at SMAN 7 Banjarmasin.

Suardi, M. (2018). *Learning & learning*. Deepublish.

Tafonao, T. (2018). The role of learning media in increasing student interest in learning. *Journal of educational communication*, 2(2), 103-114.

Widiana, I. W. (2016). Development of project assessments in science learning in elementary schools. *JPI (Indonesian Education Journal)*, 5(2), 147-157.

Yudi Sudihartono. (2020). Application of Quizizz in the Implementation of Knowledge Assessment of Training Participants at the Regional Human Resources Development Agency of South Sumatra Province.